

EXPLORING THE FACTORS CONTRIBUTING TO STUDENTS' DISRUPTIVE BEHAVIOR AND THE ESSENTIAL KNOWLEDGE TEACHERS NEED TO ADDRESS IT

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Abstract

This autobiographical study was conducted to explore why students exhibit disruptive behavior and what knowledge and skills teachers need to have to address it. Only ten teachers with a Master's degree and ten years of teaching experience in public secondary schools were the study participants. Autobiography was chosen as a pragmatic research method because direct observations or other techniques were impossible due to the closure of schools during COVID-19. The study revealed that causes of disruptive behavior included familial factors (home environment, poverty, and parents' education), social media, peer influence, and the unprofessional attitude of teachers were the main causes of disruptive behavior. It was recommended that teachers be trained in dealing with students' disruptive behavior through micro-teaching techniques based on theoretical awareness.

Keywords: Disruptive behavior; Teachers; Schools; Professional Attitude; Knowledge, classroom

1. INTRODUCTION

Disruptive behavior can be defined as behavior that creates hurdles in the effectiveness of the teaching plan of teachers or for students' learning [1], it makes the atmosphere of the classroom very crucial [2], and it further undermines teachers' teaching-learning process effectively [3]. Disruptive behavior is generally understood as behavior that violates the classroom rules and interrupts the teaching and learning process. Any behavior considered to create a barrier to others' learning or prevents the teachers' purpose of transforming knowledge [4]. Behavior that disrupts and impedes the process of learning in the class [5]; it might include misconduct, violation of discipline, misbehavior [6]; and inappropriate behavior [7]. Disruptive behavior has many damaging effects as it ruins the whole class atmosphere, teaching, and learning process.

In addition, the management skills of teachers are as necessary as their command of subject matter knowledge. Due to the disruptive behavior of students, some students drop out before completing the academic program [8]; it increases teachers' stress ([8]; disturbs self-efficacy [9]; increases burnout ratio and retention [10]. Disruptive behavior is considered a global issue and challenge for many educational institutions across the globe [11]. It becomes very challenging when the teachers' instructions are poorly managed and it becomes a leading reason for teachers' stress which sometimes results in teachers' burnout [12]. Studies on disruptive behavior found a strong relationship between teachers' inability to manage the classroom effectively and the student's disruptive behavior [13]; few studies conducted in Spain also reported the same results [14]. Disruptive behavior of students becomes a challenge for teachers in managing classrooms appropriately which leads to teachers' burnout [15]; a relationship between teachers' burnout and students' disruptive behavior exists [16]. However, the study found some other factors like sociodemographic ones, with disruptive behavior of students [17]. The income of the teaching profession is growing with time but about 50% of teachers leave the profession by the end of the fifth year similarly, huge numbers of teachers also alter their profession due to stress which stems from the responsibilities of teachers, especially classroom management [18].

Therefore, developing the managerial skills of teachers through pre-service and in-service training is necessary for effective classroom management and academic success. A study on school discipline across 41 countries found that there were many common links among countries and there were also differences based on socioeconomic level, cultural values, schools, and teachers [19]. There are many conflicting reports of disruptive behavior of students as a persisting problem for all teachers [21]. Almost forty percent of teachers left their jobs due to the disruptive behavior of children [22]; disruptive behavior affects teachers' attitudes [23]. Students with negative behavior are

at risk of early drop out, as in Australia [24], Canada Alberta Education, 2009 as cited in [25], and the USA [26]. Coordination between teachers and students helps in resolving conflicts that occur in classrooms [27]. To reduce disruptive behavior students' voices may also be listened and classroom activities may be planned accordingly. Rude, aggressive behavior does not work in classroom management [28]. Quality teaching, classroom organization, and emotional and instructional support help in meeting the disruptive behavior of students [29]. These areas were previously pointed out as critical ones without which students do not give value to education [30]. There are three main strategies of teachers through which disruptive behavior of students may be reduced and these are the preparation of teachers and activities carried out in classrooms; instruction which is the communication and response to the student's misbehavior by the teachers during classroom and; the third one is the presentation of treatment against pleasant or unpleasant consequences [31].

Teachers are facing disruptive behavior of students across the globe and this is also one of the major concerns of teachers here in Pakistan. The majority of students studying in the arts and humanities groups are more interested in politics than students of science subjects in Pakistan. The majority of teachers in Pakistan used different approaches to deal with disruptive students, such as warnings, fines, and punishment, as well as asking creative questions, teaching civics, and engaging in activities [32]. Teachers have to handle such circumstances psychologically [33]. Earlier studies which were conducted in Pakistan, were quantitative. These studies found various types of misbehaviors and general strategies of teachers to handle inappropriate behavior of students across different levels (elementary and tertiary), whereas in most cases, teachers are negatively affected by disruptive behaviors of students at the secondary level, which has not been studied yet. The researcher believes that students in secondary school, who are teenagers and belong to the peer group age, face significant emotional and social challenges due to cultural restrictions imposed by parents, elders, teachers, and others in Pakistan. There is a need to study the underlying reasons behind their disruptive behavior to gain a better understanding of the causes and develop appropriate management strategies. The current study is unique in that; it used autobiographies as a data-gathering technique, following a qualitative approach. This study focused on identifying the root causes of the disruptive behavior of students. This study was designed to answer research questions e.g., Why do students misbehave in the way they do in the class? What managerial skills and knowledge must teachers have to handle the situation properly? This study was significant as it highlighted major reasons behind the misbehavior of students and the concerns of teachers about the problems.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Theories of behaviorism assist instructors in creating a positive school atmosphere by utilizing reward and punishment systems. Skinner, a leading proponent of behavioral methodology, argued that too little attention is paid to the mind, unconscious, and environmental consequences. He believed that a behavioral approach to classroom management could be simply adopted by assessing the classroom environment, defining goals, and implementing necessary behavioral modifications [34]; [35]. Skinner's operant conditioning concepts, according to [36]), apply to classroom management (p.178). Bandura's theory is essentially a social and behavioral one in which he felt that learning occurs through observation (environment) and imitation (teacher/peer role modeling). Cognitive behavioral therapy is also effective because it assumes that cognition has a significant role in changing people's behaviors and actions. Other theories, such as [37] Choice theory, help teachers manage a good classroom environment by using a "meeting learners' needs approach". Moreover, Jones' notion of learner-directed learning is also very influential in classroom management. Another classroom management approach is aggressive, explicit communication of classroom norms and expected student behavior [38]. This research study did not adhere to a particular theory, but rather to a wide range of theories considered for satisfactory responses to the research questions.

When it comes to behavioristic theories, reinforcement in the form of praise and reward is a key aspect that is easily and primarily applicable to classroom management. Interaction and imitation, as major components of social learning theories, also play a significant role in assisting teachers in efficiently managing classrooms. Developmental theories, such as Piaget's, are also very applicable and aid teachers in understanding the developmental phases of children. Glaser's choice theory can be deemed appropriate in terms of safeguarding basic children's/human rights in the classroom and implementing democratic principles.

All sorts of behavioristic, social, cognitive, and psycho-social theories are effective in classroom management at all levels. Teachers may never be able to manage their classrooms without understanding the context, and each institute has its context including the socioeconomic position of students, community, literacy level of parents, familial environment, teachers' monitoring mechanism, and so on. Aspects of various theories must be considered, comprehended, and implemented by teachers in a variety of scenarios, and we need the time to make our teachers aware of the usage of various theories in a variety of situations.

3. METHODOLOGY

The study was qualitative, with autobiography serving as the primary data collection technique. This particular design was chosen to get detailed information on two main themes of this study. The first theme dealt with the exploration of facts about the causes of disruptive behavior of students. The second theme was to suggest what specific areas of professional development for teachers are needed. Teachers in the age range of (40-45) years with more than 15 years of teaching experience, including 10 years in public secondary schools in urban areas of district Haripur, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, were included in the sample. Based on saturation point, the final sample was determined which consisted of only 10 teachers. One of the objectives was to investigate the causes of student misbehavior, and the researcher also attempted to investigate what type of knowledge and skills teachers require for proper management of disruptive behavior among students. With time, many dimensions of education policies shifted from teacher-centered approaches to student-centered approaches. Teachers' experiences, perceptions, and techniques for dealing with misbehaviors have evolved with time. Hence, a narrative inquiry was deemed to be a better strategy for developing comprehension of this broader concept of disruptive behavior. In the narrative of autobiographies, people remember what happened, they generally organize their experiences in a logical sequence, and they discover possible implications and go with a series of events that construct society and individual life [39]. When narratives are used as methodology, researchers learn about social reality as multifaceted, complex in nature, and socially constructed through experiences of human lives in holistic and interconnected ways, which helps them learn about themselves [40]. The rationale for the selection of experienced teachers serves two reasons. First, to analyze how teachers' perceptions of children's rights may have evolved in reaction to new knowledge; psychological repercussions on children; academic degradation, lack of trust in public schools, and so on. Second, to understand the perceptions of teachers about policy changes over the last decade. The secondary classes were chosen based on the age of the children when they began breaking and violating regulations, disobeying authorities, engaging in anti-social activities, and neglecting instructors and parents as a result of an unfavorable environment or a lack of sufficient guidance.

Generally, people's confidence in publicly funded state schools has been reduced as a result of the rise of private sector engagement in education. Privately run schools are well managed, teachers' work is routinely inspected, and parents' concerns are heard by the school administration [41]. Teachers are questioned in public schools, and these schools are primarily attended by students whose parents are poor. The situation has deteriorated to the point where even low-income parents prefer to send their children to private schools [42].

Results of a systematic review of 59 studies on private schools in Asia, Africa, and the Caribbean countries indicated that private schools perform better than public schools [43]. Parents believe that the quality of education in private schools is superior to that of public schools [44]. The same situation exists in Haripur, and the majority of pupils who attend public schools come from low-income families.

Before data collection, permission was obtained from the following ethical standards. Only male secondary school teachers were involved, therefore there was no exclusion of participation based on ethnicity or gender. The inclusion of exclusively male members was due to the lower number of difficulties caused by female students in secondary schools. Since the data was obtained during the COVID-19 outbreak season, there was no loss of class time. As preventive precautions should be taken during Covid-19, the participants did not face any major risks. There was no financial incentive to participate in the study. Rapport was established, and strict confidentiality of the data was assured before data collection. Most of the data was written down and recorded on mobile with the participants' prior consent. To confirm the data's validity, a summary of the data was presented to each participant at the end of each session.

The data was thoroughly evaluated and structured following the research questions. To extract themes, each participant's responses were compared to the responses of other participants. Data was gathered and saturation points were achieved early, therefore comparable replies were categorized. The comments of various participants are described below by the study's emphasis and research questions. Perceptions of all participants are categorized in several descriptions, which are shown below.

Research Question 1: Why do students misbehave in the class?

Data: The teachers replied:

Description A:

Nowadays, parent don't have time to pay attention to their children. Firstly, the students who enrolled in our schools are coming from very poor families. These families generally live in slum areas where even basic facilities are not in place. The children remain absent from school and parents do not bother why their children are not going to school regularly. These children do not obey their parents and the environment of homes is not good. Parents quarrel with one another, they abuse one another in the presence of their children, it affects the children badly and they become rude to everyone. Most of the parents of these children are illiterate and exhibit very inappropriate behavior at home and their children copy them. These students disobey us, create a lot of problems for the whole class and they commit very unusual crimes like cheating, grabbing and snatching anything from fellows, harassing other

students in many ways, bullying and abusing are very common. The reasons behind their disruptive behavior are the illiteracy of parents, inappropriate home environment, and lack of guidance at home and school.

Emerging Themes: Parents' low socio-economic background; Illiteracy of parents and; inappropriate home environment

Description B:

The students also feel inferior due to several reasons. They know that their parents are not sending them to good schools, not investing well in them, and not fulfilling their desires to have what other children of their age have, they are demanding mobiles or other electronic gadgets and the illiterate and poor parents cannot give them mobiles; teachers' behavior is also very indifferent with their students in public schools. These realities contributed to the development of a sense of inferiority complex among students and they misbehave in schools and at home. Students at teenage generally do what they observe in the environment not what is told to them. So, in families, friends, and neighbors everywhere children are compared and when they do not come up to the expectations negative thinking about others is generated in the minds of the students. The component of training of students in schools and homes is missing.

Emerging Themes: Feelings of inferiority complex; inappropriate teachers' behavior; competition of children with other children and; absence of guidance at school and home

Description C:

Students belonging to slum areas are moving around in groups as gangs and fighting with other people. The parents residing in similar communities go out to work all day and in their absence, the young children come out of their homes or after returning from school there is nobody to keep them at home or ask them about their studies or homework, etc. They play together and they spend a lot of time gossiping and their parents do not have control over them. They do not complete their education due to not fulfilling daily assignments or homework, teachers also do not bother to take these students in confidence and guide them properly. Teachers do not talk to them or talk to their parents to bring about any positive change in students. Time has proved that such groups of youngsters usually become criminals of lower level initially and some of these get severe punishment in any form, from other people of the society or through legal procedures etc and become peaceful citizens while few of these become habitual criminals.

Emerging Themes: Poor living; Slum areas and; gangsters

Description D:

Televisions are everywhere with more than 100 active channels and all the time you have the facility to watch any type of movie. Children of poor and illiterate parents watch movies at home and they waste their time. They are teenagers, immature and they try to become heroes as they watch movies. They try to copy different characters of the movies in their daily lives. They want to adopt the style of clothing, appearance, dialogues, etc. of famous characters in movies. Due to poverty, their parent cannot fulfill their desires and they create problems at home. They don't know they cannot become the characters (of movies) at this stage of life, they are immature and disturbed. In the absence of any supervision and guidance at home, these children are free to do what they generally want.

Emerging Themes: watching movies; film stars as ideals

Description E:

Video games are everywhere in our society and more than 90% of these games are based on fighting between terrorists and security agencies. In our society, there are different places where children go to watch or play video games by paying a very minimal amount. Most of the children have these video games installed at home computers also. They play games with friends at home or in specific places (shops) etc. These video games disturbed the thinking patterns of our youth, particularly the children. The children have been affected badly by these video games and the children of well of families are also showing inappropriate behavior. These war-based activities are causes of disruptive behavior of students. Across the country, toy pistols/guns are sold openly and these are in abundance. On national days or religious festivals, almost all children from ages almost 4 to 15 years would have these toys and they used to play hide and seek as they observed in video games. This practice is not limited to the children of poor families but to the children of all types of families (from average to well-off families). This culture has also affected badly toward the attitudes and behaviors of children in Pakistan.

Emerging Themes: Video games negatively affect children

Description F:

Before 2005, there was a teacher-centered approach in all public schools, and teachers were told about children if any of these exhibited inappropriate behavior at home or anywhere in society. Parents were complaining about their children to their teachers they disobeyed at home and teachers' authority was accepted in society. In the past, if students committed any mistake, the people of society inquired have you learned this from schools? The teachers of the schools were informed and the teachers were feeling ashamed of these acts of students. Now the situation has been entirely changed, here the slogan of "Mar Nein Piyar" in the Urdu language which means (No Punishment only Love) makes the students brave. Now students did not pay attention; they knew that if any teacher punished them, they would complain against the teachers, the teachers may be dismissed from jobs in severe cases,

transferred to far-flung areas as punishment, face show cause notice, inquiries held, etc. Teachers did not bother to ask why students were not completing their home tasks; why they were not coming to classes regularly; or why they were creating a disturbance in the class. Simply teachers disown these students and now they are at their fate. According to the teachers, students' knowledge about their rights and many departmental actions taken against teachers who punished students in the past created a lot of problems on the part of students and now they disobey their teachers at school and parents at home.

Emerging Themes: Status and authority of teachers challenged; departmental disciplinary actions; no fear of children; change of policy;

Description G:

Now the complaints against students are not limited to bullying, cheating, snatching, disobeying, yelling, sleeping in class, etc., but are also receiving complaints of sexual harassment of students. It is alarming, that social media and the food they intake resulted in early puberty. The poor children joined children of well-off families who have mobiles with internet connectivity. Misbehaving students through watching movies, friends, and gangsters learn and hear a lot about sex and they get sexual orientation at an earlier age than ever before. Sexual material is in abundance in different sources of social media and the use of the internet in the absence of supervision also leads to unusual sexual intentions/crimes of students. Parents especially the illiterate ones do not know about the adverse effects of using mobile at an early age and most of the students have mobile phones in their pockets. The communication service providers give many incentives or introduce attractive cost-effective packages for youth to use mobile for communication and this also leads to making youth aggressive, and depressive and they are also unsatisfied with what they have in hand, etc. Mobile has almost finished the true relationship-building procedure from the public, everyone looks busy on mobile and no one has time for his/her near and dear ones in society.

Emerging Themes: early puberty; early sex orientation; negative media campaigns; social media; ineffective use of mobiles and; packages of communication organization for youth.

Research Question 2: What teachers should know and be able to do?

Based on the literature cited in the article's theoretical discussion, and the results of this study, it can easily be concluded that teachers are lacking in knowledge about different theories of management. Teachers don't need to know only but they should have a firm belief that students need to be understood first. Unless and until teachers try to understand the context of students, their socio-economic level, the education level of their parents, the overall environment of communities where they live, psychosocial needs, emotional disturbance, etc., they will not be able to control the disruptive behavior of students. It can also be concluded through the practices of teachers in managing the disruptive behavior of students that our teachers' capacity needs to be developed through short courses or training workshops during their jobs. Firstly, we need to help our teachers to correct their perceptions about what they can and cannot do. They need to have a "yes I can do this" attitude. They need help and knowledge to understand that they are the only ones who can correct the disruptive behavior of students and put them on the right path because students with poor backgrounds or do not have any other educated personalities in their near and dear ones to guide them properly. This is the responsibility of teachers to prepare students for a better life by transmitting up-to-date knowledge and life skills.

Moreover, our teachers need to know and understand that with the application of different principles of theories, disruptive behavior can easily be managed. They must understand the importance of well-planned lessons, a series of activities during the class, strategies for learners' involvement in the learning process, engagement learners in higher order thinking, use of reinforcement, encouragement of group activities to enhance social interaction, keeping the learning environment of the class positive, welcoming and encouraging, expecting students' behavior according to their age, adopting the democratic style of teaching, involving them in making general rules and regulations of the classroom, helping them able to control their self, being responsible for their actions, understanding familial factors which are causes of students disruptive behaviors, and developing good relations with students. Punishment strategies are still in use but it does not work well. I would like to quote a few golden words from my teacher, if an uneducated person can change the habit of (Dears, Monkeys, Elephants, Birds, snakes, etc., we generally observe in cities alongside the roads) and prepare these to be sources of their earning why we educated human being cannot change the behavior of other human beings who are superior to all creature of Allah, the Almighty with greater insight. Our teachers also need to understand that their professional attitude matters a lot and they need to improve it for the sake of their fair earnings and their contributions toward national development.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The foremost reason for children's disruptive behavior in secondary classes is the result of authoritarian dealing of teachers and this fact has been reported in several studies e.g. Teachers' professional incompetence causes disruptive behavior [45]; inadequacy of teachers as role models; teachers' professional incompetence (lack of educational/didactic expertise), and authoritarian behavior of teachers causes disruptive behavior.

The familial problems affect the learning of students in schools and this point is supported by many other researchers [46]; [47]. The environment at home sometimes causes disruptive behavior of students in schools [48];

[49], and poor housing [45]. The poor are mostly illiterate and they cannot understand the importance of the home environment in the training of children. The parents do not come to school to discuss anything with teachers regarding their kids [54]. The absence of basic needs creates many psychological, economic, and social problems among the affected and they express their feelings in the form of sometimes fighting at home. The environment becomes hostile and children in this environment exhibit this unsocial or antisocial behavior in schools also and this finding was supported by many authors/researchers, e.g., [49], [54]; imbalance development of children [49]. Similarly, students from poor backgrounds have feelings of an inferiority complex due to which they show their anger against the system and this is also supported by living in poor neighborhoods [50]. The absence of guidance in schools and at home also contributed to a disturbance among students and consequently, they exhibit antisocial or unsociable behavior in schools and communities. This finding is also in line with the results of a few other studies, degeneration of the morale of societies, [45]; students who need special attention, [49]; and attention deprivation [46]; some children only receive attention at home for misbehavior [51] and thus come to understand this behavior as the norm for seeking attention, misdirected aggression of children. Children of this age are under the great influence of their peers or friends. Friends support disruptive behavior, [49].

This study also brought to light the fact that watching movies on television regularly also spoils young children and it has been proven previously by [49] that the violence in media and internet usage creates problems for students, and they exhibit misbehavior. Actors in the movies become the ideal of these teenagers and try to be like these actors in their appearance, wearing or repeating dialogues of movies in real life. They do not understand the difference between the real situations of life and the situations shown in the movies. Exposure to violence leads to misbehavior in children [52]. Parents are unaware in most of the cases and the students display disruptive behaviors in schools. This study found that teachers' authority has been challenged due to changes in the policy of dealing with students in the schools as previously reported by [21]; [4]. Teachers used to be quite authoritative, and the community was on their side, which meant parents and other community members complained about students' misconduct. Parents are no longer cooperating with teachers, and some even threaten them. Similarly, a study conducted by Rayment [48] revealed that many parents had violent and aggressive views toward instructors, and their children also demonstrated signs of aggression, disruptive behavior, and hostility in schools. Nowadays, students are out of control and causing several problems in schools.

Teachers need to be trained according to the changing situation and patterns of human life. Currently, the students are very much cleverer than the teachers and they played different tricks to dodge the teachers. Quality education mainly depends upon the quality of instructional activity in the classroom setting [55].

5. CONCLUSIONS

The students enrolled in public schools generally belonged to poor families. The overall public doesn't trust schooling at public schools. Parents who cannot afford the fees charged in private schools send their children to public schools in Pakistan. Based on the results presented above following conclusions were drawn;

Immoral home environment due to parents' illiteracy, irresponsible and rude behavior at home, misunderstandings between parents, and poverty caused disruptive behavior of students. Inferiority complex due to studying in public schools, failure in fulfillment of students' desires (mobiles and other electronic gadgets), and inappropriate attitude of teachers towards students were the causes of disruptive behavior among students. The unavailability of proper guidance from teachers and parents made students of slum areas gangsters who moved around their respective communities and fought with other people. Our television programs telecast movies and the students of slum areas usually watched these movies most of the time and they tried to imitate what they watched in movies as heroes.

There is a sense of developing competition among children within and out of the family, in the neighborhood, and even with the children of friends. It creates hate, jealousy, rivalry, depression, anxiety, and stress among students. Parents don't have time to pay attention to their children. The children remain absent from school and parents do not bother why their children are not going to school regularly. Parents quarrel with one another, they abuse one another in the presence of their children, it affects the children badly and they become rude to everyone. Most of the parents of these children are illiterate and exhibit very inappropriate behavior at home and their children copy them. Feelings of inferiority due to the unavailability of mobiles or other such things which are desired by the children of the poor families. The poor live in areas where there is no facility and young children of that particular society move around as gangsters. In the form of groups, the youngsters commit many types of criminal activities due to which they become habitual offenders. Video games are considered a great contributor to the disruptive behavior of students from all types of families. In Pakistan, most video games are destructive; in these games, there is a fight between terrorists and security agencies. Fighting video games were abundant in Pakistan and students used to play these video games and exhibited the same characters in their free time. The government of Pakistan imposed sanctions on exporting such video games for the last few years. Most school-going children in Pakistan used to buy artificial arm toys in varieties at national and religious festivals (Eid Ul Hedha & Eid Ul Fitr). Students grown up in these cultures had tendency of fighting, snatching and cheating. It is alarming, that social media and the food they intake resulted in early puberty. The poor children joined children of well-off families who have

mobiles with internet connectivity. Misbehaving students through watching movies, friends, and gangsters learn and hear a lot about sex and they get sexual orientation at an earlier age than ever before. Sexual material is in abundance in different sources of social media and the use of the internet in the absence of supervision also leads to unusual sexual intentions/crimes of students.

Teachers neither bothered to pay individual attention to the students nor did they talk to the parents of the students to take any corrective measures. Teachers-centered pedagogy has been changed to student-centered pedagogy since 2008 in Pakistan. In the former position, teachers were responsible for any of the students' mistakes within and outside of school. Teachers used to ask students and punish them if they received any complaints against them. For the last decade, teachers were strictly forbidden to punish students and the students usually did not follow teachers' instructions as they knew teachers couldn't punish them. Freedom of the students made them bold and to some extent, impudent and rude. In that scenario, there was a need to develop the capacity of teachers to handle the students adequately. Instead, the teachers felt insecure and they did not bother to take any responsibility.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, teachers and students must develop a set of rules and regulations for classroom collaboratively and these should be posted in each classroom. Teachers should discuss these time and again whenever feel necessary with students and colleagues. Teachers need to share their expectations with students and what they expect from students in discussions. Expectations or positive behaviors must be shared at the start of classes so that everyone knows what is expected from him/her. Teachers should share information in agreeable ways and means to be adopted as routine matters e.g., how to enter the class? Who to participate in the discussion? Who to ask questions? How to share things with fellows? How to sit and do work in class? How to participate in learning actively? How to submit homework? How to work in group activities? Teachers should try to improve his/her practices and revisit these time and again, concerning time, delivery of instructions, and dealing with disruptive behavior sustainably and consistently. Teachers should try to enhance the participation of students so that they learn by themselves in social settings through interaction and imitation following principles of social learning theories.

Teachers also need to adopt behavioral approaches to dealing with students by praising students' positive contributions within the classroom or outside of the classroom. Teachers should apply strategies of praise and reward transparently and consistently. There should be defined consequences for disruptive behavior and teachers need to adopt and apply those consequences transparently. Teachers also need to keep in mind the different stages of development of students and what can be expected during each developmental stage so that expectations may become realistic. Teachers need to develop close ties with parents to maintain good practices both at home and school levels for better training of students through different stages of development. Teachers also need to adopt a democratic style of dealing with students by giving them choices according to choice theory and making them responsible for their actions. Teachers should also try to adopt basic principles of different theories so that these can be applied according to the level of the class and the age of the students. Through reflective teaching strategies, students can be kept busy in the learning process because, in higher-order learning students need to be attentive and focused. When instructions are very interesting and challenging students think there will be no or very minimal disturbance on the part of students. Teachers should carefully plan activities of learning and ways to involve students in these activities. Teachers should try to make different group activities and keep on changing group formation and roles of participants as well e.g., changing in group leadership. Teachers should create a conducive learning environment in the classroom where everyone can learn according to his/her own pace of learning. He should try to adopt different techniques during the delivery of instruction based on different learning styles and levels of bits of intelligence. During class teachers should have a plan to involve students of different capacities in the learning process e.g., students with high intelligence or who are very smart in learning can be engaged as supervisors of groups and helpers of their fellows' learning. The dull mind or below-average students may be instructed with great care and repeatedly so that they may not be involved in any other disruptive activities. Teachers should have a very good relationship with each student so that he/she can talk to anyone privately, motivate and encourage them to learn.

7. IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

This study has many implications for the institutions of developing countries like Pakistan and underdeveloped countries across the globe. This study has greater implications in the Gulf region, where the students' disruptive behavior is reported frequently. There is a shortage of local teachers, and the job description includes accommodating attitude of teachers in unusual classrooms. Most of the native students don't follow teachers' instructions, not because of poverty, but due to irresponsible attitudes and lack of motivation for learning. The countries of the African region also face educational challenges, including the disruptive behavior of students and this study has equal implications for their educational institutions.

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